

Beyond Marginality: Exploring the Root Causes of Gabooye Marginalization in Somaliland

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Abstract

The study discusses the origins of marginalization of Gabooye people in Somaliland. A review of existing literature reveals some consistent patterns of marginalization, however, it has been unable to explore the roots of those patterns. Using the methodological approach of Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT), this study examines the root cause(s) of marginalization using data collected during 18 months of field work in Hargeisa, Somalia (June 2022 – Dec. 2023). Data were collected through both qualitative methods (16 in-depth interviews, 6 focus groups, and 25 archival testimonies) using respondents who represented several social categories in Somaliland society. Those categories include traditional leaders, members of the Gabooye community, young adults, and political elites. Results indicate that marginalization derives from colonial policies instituted by Britain in the early part of the twentieth century which disarticulated previously interconnected oral-based kingdoms, specifically Tumaal and Yibir kingdoms of the Gabooye people. Furthermore, results also demonstrate how marginalization continues today because of purity myths, occupational stigmatism, and genealogical exclusion. Marginalization is made possible through a number of mechanisms including spatial segregation of Gabooye people into segregated communities; limited access to education and job training necessary to function in an increasingly globalized economy; and symbolic political representation in the form of electoral participation without corresponding levels of political influence or power. Ultimately, this study provides evidence that marginalization exists among Gabooye people due to structural factors rather than being merely coincidental and/or local; therefore, providing empirical support for Weber's Status Group Theory and Gramsci's Hegemonic Theory within the context of Somali society. Additionally, the fact that I am a scholar of Somali ancestry permitted me to engage with insiders' grounded perspectives. Finally, this study recommends a multi-dimensional approach to address the problem of dismantling the caste-like structure of marginalization; i.e., legal, cultural, political, and discursively.

Keywords: Gabooye, grounded theory, marginalization, Somaliland.

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Introduction

Somaliland, previously known as the British Protectorate of Somaliland, has proclaimed its own self-government status since declaring an independent state from Somalia in 1991. Somaliland's success to build a relatively democratic government and peaceful society is somewhat mitigated by significant social inequality. The most notable example of this are minority populations such as the Gabooye who are historically marginalized due to over three hundred years of social and political stratification related to ethnicity, economic and social class, goat caste, and political power (Bade, 2023). Although there is considerable cultural, linguistic, and religious similarity between the Gabooye and the majority Somali population, they continue to be marginalized due to the nation's historical clan system and colonial legacy which continues to influence current political structures (Ekman, 2021, P.168; Vitturini, 2020a, P.4).

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The Gabooye have traditionally been involved in occupations such as blacksmithing, hairdressing, circumcision and leatherwork. In many historical cases these occupations were seen as “unclean” by the traditional pastoralist Somali clans and therefore socially marginalized (Ekman, 2021, P.177; Eno, 2005, P.40). Historically these occupational stigmas allowed dominant clans to restrict political agency of the Gabooye by limiting them from marrying into clans and therefore limiting their influence in the political sphere (Ekman, 2021, P.225).

Historical evidence demonstrates that the Gabooye’s marginalization is more than an issue of economic status it is also the result of how the social construct of Somali identity privileges Arab ancestry and pastoralist culture over others. This means those individuals or groups that do not fit within this form of clan based, race based identity are systemically marginalized (Ekman, 2021, P.168-173; Eno, 2005, P.40).

Colonialism and post-colonialism further reinforced the power dynamic relationship between Gabooye and the dominant Somali clans. During the period of British colonial administration (1886-1960), the British used the method of Indirect Rule to govern Somalia. Indirect Rule refers to a governing style where the ruling authority uses local leaders to administer the affairs of the population while ignoring subaltern populations (such as the Gabooye). As in most colonies and protectorates throughout history, the British ignored the Gabooye and instead worked directly with the dominant Somali clans to implement policies and enforce administrative decisions (Vitturini, 2020, P.42).

Urbanisation occurred during the colonial era as did changes in the types of labor available. However, at the same time colonial practices reproduced discrimination against subordinate subdivisions (like the Gabooye) by placing limits on economic mobility opportunities (Ekman, 2021, P.140; Eno, 2005, 2008). The institutional legacy of these colonial practices shaped the governance structure of post independence states and continued to limit the Gabooye from participation in state political representation structures and equitable access to state resources as economic capital (Ekman, 2021, P.226). Even though Siyad Barre (1969-1991) made attempts to eliminate clan-based politics during his regime he was unable to eliminate the systemic marginalization of the Gabooye. Some policies developed to promote inclusion for certain clans, including the Gabooye, did little to address their marginalization and exclusion (Ekman, 2021, P.181).

The contemporary literature on the Gabooye is dominated by the work of international academics such as Vitturini (2016, 2017, 2020b, 2020a) and Ekman (2021), and a limited number of studies authored by Somali scholars such as Eno (2005, 2008), Eno & Eno, (2010), and (Lehman & Eno, 2003). While much of the recent literature addresses issues related to Somalia, where ethnic, linguistic or dialectical, and physical differences among populations add complexity to an analysis of how marginalization occurs, Somaliland is particularly interesting case since Somaliland is internally relatively homogeneous. People in Somaliland all speak one language, they have one religion, they physically and culturally practice in the same ways – so there will be no noise added to the atypical responses due to non-clinical variables. As a result, while marginalization of the Gabooye persists in Somaliland because of structural and symbolic reasons, the lack of research done on this local community makes it a rich source of study.

Thus, this study fills this void by collecting first-hand narrative accounts from members of the Gabooye community, examining those accounts to determine what structural elements contribute to their marginalization, and through a constructivist grounded theory methodology provides voice to the members of the Gabooye community within academic discourse. This study asks: What are some of the root causes of the persistent marginalization of the Gabooye population in Somaliland? The study aims to generate empirically based theory through answering this question and to present a culturally situated interpretative framework for understanding caste-like marginalization in a Somali post-colonial Muslim context.

The Gabooye: Identity, History and Marginalization

One of the oldest and most marginalized social groups in Somali society is the Gabooye. Unlike the majority Somali clans, whose history is based on pastoralism and nobility, the Gabooye constitute the periphery of the social hierarchy. Historically, they were seen as outside the mainstream due to their

occupations and histories that portrayed them as “others” (Ekman, 2021: P.168; Vitturini, 2020: P.24). The category of “Gabooye” refers to various hereditary and minority communities of people including Tumaal, Yibir, Madhiban and Musa-Dheriyo. These communities face the same forms of discrimination against one another (Ekman, 2021, p. 22).

Historically, Somali society has been organized in a hierarchical system based on clans. As a result, the Gabooye were classified as lower-status minorities and were denied access to political representation, intermarriage rights, and diya-paying alliances (Vitturini, 2017, p. 4). For centuries, the Gabooye were relegated to the occupational roles of blacksmiths, leather workers, shoemakers, and potters. These occupations have traditionally been viewed as impure by the dominant clans (Grottanelli, 1972; Mansuur, 2016). Although these skills are crucial to the functioning of Somali society, they contributed to both the stigma associated with these occupations and systemic exclusion from participating in it.

Colonial rule institutionalized the exclusion of the Gabooye. During British rule in Somaliland, the dominant Somali clans were designated as political intermediaries. This designation reinforced a power structure that would systematically exclude the Gabooye from decision-making processes (Vitturini, 2017, p. 77). Urbanization during the colonial era provided opportunities for economic mobility for some segments of the Gabooye population. They had access to urban labor markets in cities like Hargeisa and Boroma but this occurred under highly restrictive conditions (Vitturini, 2020, p. 11). The British formally recognized Gabooye leaders as independent diya-paying entities and politicized them to a certain extent (Cassanelli, 1982).

Collective identity among “Gabooye” formed in the post-colonial era, replacing derogatory terms such as “Midgaan,” “Sab,” etc. (Vitturini, 2017, p. 4). The renaming process was part of a broader effort to reclaim identities and challenge structural exclusions embedded in social institutions. However, many members of Tumaal, Yibir, and Madhiban communities do not identify with the broader “Gabooye” identity. This reflects current internal struggles over who identifies with the “Gabooye” community and what does that mean.

In addition to the existing social divisions between Gabooye communities across Somalia, there are significant numbers of Gabooye residents living in the Daami neighborhood surrounding Hargeisa and other physically separate neighborhoods (Vitturini, 2017, p. 18). Representation in governance for Gabooye is very limited and despite increases in political participation and economic opportunity, continuing patterns of discrimination exist in areas such as employment, education and social mobility (Ekman, 2021, p. 256).

Therefore, this study builds on prior studies of Gabooye experiences by incorporating direct interviews with Gabooye individuals and assessing the underlying causes for their marginalization. Therefore, this study will assess root causes of Gabooye marginalization.

The Intersection of Social, Economic, and Political Marginality: a Review of the Gabooye Community in Somaliland

Although there are many dimensions of marginality, it generally refers to a multi-faceted process of construction whereby the process of construction creates a position for individuals from which they cannot participate in society and therefore do not gain equal social, economic or political power. As a result of being ethnically marginalised, the Gabooye community in Somaliland have experienced long-term discrimination, socio-economic marginalisation and political exclusion (Vitturini, 2020; Ekman, 2021). Many researchers such as Vitturini (2023), Ekman (2021), Kusow, (2004) and Eno (2005, 2008) also demonstrate that this form of marginalisation is both economically related, as well as socially and culturally embedded, and politically established through institutions and systems that produce and reproduce marginalisation. This has resulted in limited opportunities for the Gabooye in accessing resources, political representation and social mobility and as such, their status is determined by structural factors rather than simply being a product of economic disadvantage.

Additionally, stigmatisation of the Gabooye has been incorporated into local mythology and stories about professions, as well as enforced endogenous marriages in a way that has created a caste like system within

Somali society (Ekman, 2021: P.22; Eno, 2005: P.40). In line with Kusow (2004) and Eno (2008) the four major clans in Somalia have promoted a discourse of homogeneity based upon Arab blood that excludes those who are perceived to be unassimilable into this racialized and clan-based identity (Ekman, 2021: P.168). The Gabooye group, seen as outside of the traditional Somali identity, have suffered stigma because of the nature of their supposed ancestry and association with “unpure” occupations including blacksmithing, shoemaking and hair dressing (Ekman, 2021: P.177). Symbolic exclusion has had significant effects for generations creating inter generational ghettoisation: denial of right to inter marry, limited mobility and cultural disengagement. The Somali language structure is said to lack appreciation for diversity and is supported by an assimilationist ideology, which further isolates marginalised groups such as the Gabooye (Eno and Kusow, 2014).

Social stigma has been the primary method through which the Gabooye class has experienced social exclusion, but they have also experienced marginalization based on economic disparities. The Gabooye class has experienced an absence of access to financial resources, land, and financial opportunities (Ekman 2021, Vitturini 2020b). In contrast, wealth was accumulated by dominant clans such as the Darod and Dir through trade and pastoralism. Historically, however, the Gabooye were denied the right to own property which forced many of them into service-oriented and craft-based economies (Ekman, 2021: p. 177) . The majority of high status jobs in Somaliland are controlled by clan-based networks creating a “closed” labor market that excludes individuals from the Gabooye class from accessing the highest paying jobs available. Colonial policies designed to create a global economy created economic systems that further divided Somalis along lines of class. This division occurred because one group was positioned at the top of global capitalist hierarchies while another group was at the bottom (Vitturini, 2020b: p. 42). Urban development did provide new employment options for some members of the Gabooye class, but they continued to be financially dependent upon the clans who owned property and resources.

Political marginalization of the Gabooye is arguably the most deeply ingrained form of marginalization. Political structure in Somaliland remains heavily based on clan affiliations. Therefore, it creates great difficulty for non-clan affiliated groups to obtain representation in government (Bade, 2024). As opposed to the clans that can draw on their family ties for political access and opportunity, the Gabooye do not have enough clan support to allow them to run for government positions (Ekman, 2021: p. 226). Elections in Somaliland are based on clan affiliation and therefore give no electoral advantage or bargaining position to minority groups including the Gabooye (Ekman, 2021: p. 258). Although Somaliland adopted a multi-party system of governance, this did not eliminate the existing structural barriers in governance that continue to limit the ability of the Gabooye to participate in decision-making processes (Vitturini, 2020). Minority rights generally lack protection under laws which allows them to act as actors. They experience systematic barriers to political participation and their rights are subordinate.

The historical experience of the marginalization of the Gabooye is an example of the long-term marginalization of a group of people in a hierarchical system; regardless of changes in government or economy. Colonial authorities initially neglected the Gabooye during the period of the British Protectorate (1884–1960), due to the fact that their primary approach to governing Somalia was through cooperation with the powerful Somali clans (Vitturini, 2020b). However, urban development under colonial rule gave the Gabooye opportunities to move towards better lives. When the Gabooye moved into cities such as Hargeisa looking for specialized employment, they became one of the mobile populations. This can be viewed as a moment of movement toward greater inclusion in terms of being recognized by colonial authority as well as having an opportunity to enter into relationships with other groups. For instance, colonial authorities came to accept new Gabooye leaders (caaqils) and included them in diya-paying groups. These developments represented a major shift from previous discriminatory practices (Cassanelli, 1982). Despite these changes, colonial economic policies did little to address the very deep-rooted structures of discrimination that limited Gabooye participation in wealth creation and governance.

Under Siyad Barre’s regime (1969-1991) there were efforts to eliminate clan-based politics and promote national identity (Ekman, 2021: P. 181). As part of Barre’s effort to dismantle clannishness, he promoted

loyalty to the State. This allowed previously excluded minority groups (such as the Gabooye) to become more involved in the political and economic life of Somalia (Hoehne, 2015). Additionally, as a result of Barre’s promotion of national identity, some members of the Gabooye rose to key positions in the political and military elite. At least at first, this can be seen as evidence that the Gabooye had finally achieved a measure of political and social equality. But while clan identities were officially suppressed by Barre, they continued to play a role in resource distribution and appointment to official posts. Thus, even though Barre was able to create a “modern” type of politics, the structural exclusion of the Gabooye could not be totally eliminated (Vitturini, 2017: P. 253).

Since the fall of the Somali State and subsequent civil war, the post-1991 era has been a mixed bag for the Gabooye. Because of mass displacement of marginalized Somali communities (Vitturini, 2017: P. 210), so many Gabooye families were forced out of centers where they earned money and therefore were cut off from customary means of earning income and faced increased discrimination in an increasingly fractured society. After Somaliland’s post-war governance system reinstated the Gabooye into some political and social structures (rights etc.), they also maintained second-class citizen status (Vitturini, 2020b). There have been numerous legal advances for affirmative action and others calling for it; but structural exclusion still continues to prevent full involvement of Gabooye in economic, social and political life (Ekman, 2021 P. 256).

This form of marginalization parallels forms of oppression found in societies with castes. While rooted in the specific historical and cultural context of Somalis, Gabooye marginalization shares striking similarities with forms of hereditary exclusion in other contexts. The table below provides a comparative overview that illustrates common ways that social marginalization occurs.

Table 1. Comparative Dimensions of Caste Like Exclusion

Dimension	Gabooye (Somaliland)	Dalits (India)	Osu (Nigeria)	Burakumin (Japan)
Basis of Exclusion	Genealogy, Occupation, Myth/sacred and profane	Birth-based caste, impurity	Ancestral slavery, ritual impurity	Ancestral outcast status
Endogamy	Strictly enforced by dominant clans	Legally outlawed but persists	Deeply entrenched	Socially practiced
Social Access	Excluded from marriage with few endogomies, Socially segregated, Social mobility	Limited despite quotas	Excluded from community rituals	Spatially and socially segregated
Political Power	Token roles	Reserved seats, limited agency	Limited rights, low visibility	Symbolic inclusion only
Economic Access	Denied loans obs via clan networks	Affirmative action policies	Informal economic exclusion	Discrimination in hiring

Methodology

The study used constructivist grounded theory (CGT) to explore the structural and experiential aspects of Gabooye marginalization in Somaliland. Charmaz’s, (2006) Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) was utilized, as this is particularly skilled at capturing the lived experiences of participants, as well as co-constructing meaning between the researcher and the subjects, providing a context sensitive understanding of systemic exclusion. The positionality of the researcher as a Somali scholar facilitated cultural engagement and built trust in the data collection phase. A reflexivity journal was kept throughout the research process to provide a record of positional biases and ensure the integrity of interpretations.

Data were collected in Hargeisa, from June 2022 to August 2023. In total, 65 participants contributed: 40 were directly involved with a total of 16 interviews and six focus group discussions conducted, with an additional 25 testimonies collected from archival broadcasts of Universal TV. Participants were selected using purposive and theoretical sampling strategies to ensure they represented diversity in terms

of perspectives (including politicians and civil servants (7), traditional leaders (8), youth (5), and the Daami neighborhood (20).

Data analysis was conducted following (Diirie et al., 2023) stepwise coding process, starting with initial coding (line by line) followed by focused and axial coding to construct conceptual relationships across categories. Neither new analytical insights were arising, so the theoretical saturation was achieved. Interview, focus group, and archival triangulation increased validity and minimized recall bias. Ethical approval was obtained from Ankara Yildirim Beyazit University and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. In order to protect anonymity, unique codes were assigned to participants. This process, grounded in empirical and ethical triangulation, ensured that findings were both empirically robust and theoretically informed.

Results

Historically, there were many problems that caused the marginalization of the Gabooye in Somaliland. The Gabooye are also fragmented by an oral history that recounts how they lost their kingdoms (Tumaal & Yabir). Colonial legacy and administration, particularly the British Protectorate system created systemic barriers that segregated them and established inequality that persisted for generations. Socially and culturally, the practices of clan loyalty and the spread of false myths about the Gabooye continue to establish narratives that separate the Gabooye from the rest of Somalian society. Systemic barriers to access education, jobs, and housing in urban areas remain because Somaliland institutions and social structures have failed to create policy or structure that would eliminate bias against the Gabooye.

Figure 1. Root Causes of Gabooye Marginalization Grounded in the Data

Historical Factors

The long history of the Gabooye’s marginalization is a product of many decades of marginalization in oral history. Historically there were two powerful kingdoms, the Tumaal and the Yibir, where both economically and culturally the Gabooye were a prominent part. According to traditional Gabooye stories they fell into pieces because of political strife as well as attack from outside forces causing the people to be dispersed geographically and occupationally separated. However this is not a formalized account of their story within literature. Colonialism then exacerbated their lack of inclusion through establishing clan hierarchy as a result of treaties with dominant clans that excluded further marginalized clans from the very beginning of colonial administration. In addition to colonialism, the post-colonial state also created systems of government that continued to maintain the same political marginalization as before through

the use of clan based systems. As such the legacy of historical marginalization has been the basis for the modern day social and political structures that continue to isolate the Gabooye.

Oral sources indicate that as the Tumaal and Yibir Kingdoms began to fall apart there was a start to marginalize the Gabooye including physically and socially isolating them. Historically, according to oral accounts, they had been a significant part of economic and culture but as a result of internal strife and foreign encroachment, over time they lost power and were restricted to low status labor.

"...The Tumaal Kingdom, known for its skilled blacksmiths and craftsmen, was not only a center for trade but also a hub for cultural exchange. Their downfall was not just a loss of territory but a significant erosion of their societal status, which was manipulated by other rising Somali clans seeking dominance" (INT-P3, Female, 62).

"....The Yibir Kingdom, which had considerable influence in spiritual and ceremonial roles, saw its decline as external influences and internal conflicts destabilized their standing. What followed was not merely a loss but a complete transformation in how their heritage was perceived and valued" (INT-P7, Male, 70).

These kingdoms did not fall merely politically; the social and economic consequences lasted for ages. In Somali community, the Gabooye historically played a significant role in society, but were ultimately ostracised from and stigmatized by society, with their skills denigrated and status diminished.

".....Our history was rewritten by those who overpowered us. What was once a sign of craftsmanship became a mark of shame" (INT-P6, Male, 66).

The British Protectorate of Somaliland's colonial project enhanced this marginalization in a way that embedded a clan-based administrative structure into its governmental operations; which did not only add to the already established power dynamics as it related to the dominance of certain clans over Gabooye families, but also added to and solidified the governmental structures on the national level that continued to exclude those marginalized Gabooye groups. The British Protectorate administered Somaliland using local clan leaders and thus structured their government around the pre-existing social hierarchy.

".....Under colonial rule, the strategic importance of supporting dominant clans became apparent. The British saw it as a way to ensure easier control over the territories by relying on local power structures. Unfortunately, this meant further sidelining the Gabooye, whose historical marginalization was deepened by colonial policies" (INT-P9, Male, 78).

Marginalizing the Gabooye was due to colonial policies' reinforcement of pre-existing divisions rather than creating them. In addition to reinforcing those divisions, colonial economic policy undermined Gabooye's ability to be included as part of mainstream society.

"....Not only were we excluded from decision-making authority, but the colonial rulers placed an additional tax on our handicraft products thereby limiting our ability to maintain our living standards, which were already limited within the hierarchy of society" (INT-P10, Male, 60).

"...Colonial authorities used our historically created divisions (which stemmed from rivalry and occupational hierarchies) to create structure around those divisions thereby guaranteeing that the ruling powers remained with the clans that could most readily be manipulated and controlled. As such, the colonial authorities reinforced and entrenched the social isolation of the Gabooye and other fringe groups." (INT-P8, Female, 55).

While there was a shift toward independence after the colonial period, the post-colonial state not only did not eliminate colonial legacies but also embedded marginalization into clan-based forms of government. While this was a time of optimism regarding entrepreneurial opportunities leading to political domination by successful families, those entrepreneurial opportunities simultaneously insured that similar exclusionary practices that characterized earlier periods (i.e., political suppression), would persist however in different forms.

"...Post-Independence leaders merely followed the colonial model by utilizing clan ties as a means to solidify their power. Thus while previous forms of marginalization were simply maintained they were now institutionalized within the very framework of national governance" (INT-P5, Female, 68).

“...We had hoped that Independence would represent a change for all of us yet for us it represented nothing but more of the same. The families that had collaborated with the British continued to govern and make sure no one challenged their position of power by maintaining our marginalization” (INT-P2, Male, 70).

“...Independence didn't remove our marginalization, it legitimized it. We were outside looking in during the British regime, we remain so today despite being ruled by our own people” (INT-P12, Male, 64).

Structures of exclusion persisted resulting in virtually non-existent political representation for the Gabooye. Their voices were not heard or considered in decisions regarding governance and their economic condition worsened.

Sociocultural Factors

Clannism, Occupational Stigma & Stereotypes create a framework for stigmatizing the Gabooye creating a cycle of exclusion. They do not belong to one of the major clans therefore they are not able to participate in politics nor be represented politically. The Gabooye do not marry into other clans and therefore cannot improve their socio-economic position. Socially, myths about the Gabooye being cursed or impure create an additional stigma against the community. Their occupations (shoe-making, blacksmiths, barbers) are viewed by society as base. These biases are deeply ingrained in education, employment, and housing which results in generational cycles of marginalization.

Additionally, it is noted that individuals categorized as a low-status minority group such as the Gabooye have historically been excluded from membership in large clan alliances. This has resulted in limited political representation, opportunities for social mobility, and economic opportunities.

“...here, your clan is your identity, your protection, your chance at a better life. But for us, being Gabooye means you start life with fewer opportunities, less respect, and more barriers” (INT-P24, Male, 38).

This marginalization extends to governance, where clan alliances dictate leadership and decision-making processes. Community members express frustration over institutionalized favoritism, which reinforces discrimination.

“....most of the time, it feels like the government and the laws are not made for us. They cater to the majority clans, ensuring their dominance and continuity, while we remain on the outskirts of every decision-making process” (INT-P25, Female, 29).

Discrimination on the basis of clan extends beyond politics to jobs and services. Social networks, essential for obtaining jobs and business opportunities, systematically exclude the Gabooye.

“...When businesses hire, they want recommendations. If you have a Gabooye name, or ancestry, then there's a pause, a rethinking, as if you're less capable because of your geneology” (INT-P26, Male, 33).

This informal but powerful system of marginalization is also an important part of how those forced to live in the margins do so and it shapes spatial segregation through unequal access to housing and communities.

“....In our town, there are areas where Gabooye are unwelcome to purchase houses. It is not official policy, but everyone knows where 'we can go' and where 'we cannot.' It's a community rule that whispers” (INT-P27, Female, 45).

Lifelong myths and stereotypes have deepened the marginalization of the Gabooye in history. Such beliefs depict the community as cursed, impure, or spiritually lesser, legitimizing their purging.

“.... people still whisper that we are cursed, that our ancestors did something terrible to deserve this status. These stories are transmitted like heirlooms, poisoning generations after generations to look against us” (INT-P29, Female, 52).

Such myths are passed down from child to child through socialization, which impacts the treatment of younger generations of Gabooye in schools and communities.

“.....my child came home crying because classmates said to him he shouldn't touch them, that he's bad luck. These kids don't come up with these ideas; they get it from home.” (INT-P31, Female, 34).

Such ideas inform the interactions of many in their daily lives, including economic ones, where Gabooye workers and owners of business often encounter systematic bias.

“.....at marketplaces, you can see the reluctance when people buy from us, as if our touch would soil whatever we are selling. It is the old myths that are at work, the unspoken idea that we are unclean.” (INT-P30, Male, 46).

The stigma plays out in community events as well, with Gabooye being physically excluded or silenced.

“At local gatherings, we are frequently divided into separate tables, or on occasion group lists, and we are not even invited. As if by our presence we will taint the affair. This is the myths in acte isolating us in our own society” (INT-P33, F, 41).

Marginalization is not static; it is generationally inherited and ensures socioeconomic disparities will remain. Gabooye children are raised to internalise exclusion, creating a cycle of disadvantaged inheritance that is difficult to escape.

“..... our kids sometimes are isolated or bullied at school due to the clan. Teachers, those who are supposed to protect them, sometimes act like it's normal for the Gabooye kids to be treated this way” (INT-P28, Male, 40).

The exclusion also plays out in the legal and social systems, as Gabooye individuals experience discrimination in conflicts or legal disputes.

“And.....when there is a problem, a theft or a fight, the Gabooye are often accused without proof. It's the stereotype of us being troublemakers, embedded into the same myths that disvalue us” (INT-P32, Male, 39).

Exclusion sociocultural is still a barrier to Gabooye in Somaliland integration. Clannism and occupational stigma, rooted in social myths and historical biases, have reinforced their marginalization. The rigid clan hierarchy limits social mobility, political representation and economic opportunities. Persistent myths of the Gabooye as culturally distinct and impure perpetuate social discrimination across education, employment and intermarriage, clubbing all Gabooye under the same banner. Such entrenched social exclusion is passed down through generations, making structural change elusive.

Systematic Factors

Historical and contemporary exclusion of Gabooye in Somaliland continues in all three (social, political, economic) spheres. Historically, and currently, social exclusion has been a major obstacle for Gabooye in both achieving an education and/or finding employment. As such, as a result of being socially excluded, the Gabooye are left with low socio-economic status. They are therefore unable to function independently of humanitarian assistance. In addition to social barriers, educational barriers prevent them from attending school. Limited resources and fewer available scholarship funds restrict their mobility. Despite achieving high levels of academic achievement by Gabooye students, this is typically met with skepticism regarding how they were able to achieve it as a member of the Gabooye. Employers who are discriminatory towards the Gabooye also contribute to the marginalization of the community by rating Gabooye applicants lower than other candidates during the interview process; thereby reducing their potential to increase income through promotion into better paying jobs and limiting their potential to find new job openings. Creating businesses for the Gabooye people through loans and networking is very difficult.

The urban segregation of Gabooye neighborhoods results in the creation of neglected areas in terms of public services, sanitation, and infrastructure. These are not merely unfortunate circumstances but are intentional and represent the institutionalized social exclusion that exists to continue to exclude the Gabooye people from Somaliland mainstream society. Social mobility can occur in many ways, but primarily through education. However, Gabooye children encounter open systemic discrimination in schools, educational resources, and scholarships.

“..... our children get bullied and ostracised in schools. They are frequently made to feel unwelcome not just by their peers but by the educational system itself, which appears engineered to keep them on the fringes.” (INT-P40, Female, 42).

Gabooye students face a self fulfilling prophecy when teachers have low expectations about to their performance. Infrastructure deficiencies, such as a lack of applicable facilities, and educational resources are prominent in the neighborhoods inhabited by Gabooye.

“.....The general state of schools located in Gabooye neighborhoods is dismal. They lack basic facilities such as libraries and computers, which other schools take for granted” (INT-P42, Female, 30).

Access to higher education and career opportunities are further limited by a lack of scholarships that could help Gabooye students, not to mention, contribute in bridging educational gaps.

“.....Our children are one of the most underrepresented people in terms of scholarships or support programs available to them, yet they need them the most. It’s almost like the system has put in place ways to keep them down.” (INT-P43, Male, 47).

“...Even their meritocracy, has students who best perform among Gabooye to be doubted about their achievements. even when Gabooye students excel, they are frequently doubted on their skills. It’s like their success is always up for debate, it discourages any young person trying to create a future” (INT-P44, Female, 35).

Such disparities in education prevent Gabooye youth from qualifying for and accessing higher education and professional jobs, perpetuating poverty and social marginalisation. The Gabooye are often prevented from getting hired, promoted or from receiving loans, which severely hampers their economic mobility.

“.....In job interviews, when they learn you are Gabooye the tenor changes. The warmth vanishes and all of a sudden the job is unreachable” (INT-P45, Male, 34). Gabooye cannot climb the employment ladder even when they have jobs, and many are consigned to dead end positions with no chance of advancement.

“....it’s not just about getting a job, it’s about retaining a job and advancing in a job.” We frequently find Gabooye staff who hold the same junior roles without a genuine avenue for career progression” (INT-P46, Female, 29).

Entrepreneurship is another struggle, with limited access to loans and investment opportunities leading to financial exclusion for many Gabooye business owners.

“.....our businesses suffer as well. Loans and business support service is often conditional, meaning that there is no way for Gabooye entrepreneurs to gain the access” (INT-P47, Male, 41).

In addition to diversifying workplaces, the upper class of corporate Gabooye applicants also faces refusal to hire due to an anti-Gabooye mindset, further highlighting the disparity between the rhetoric of inclusiveness and the reality of hiring practices.

“.....even in places of employment that boast about diversity, there’s a reluctance to employ Gabooye. It’s an unspoken rule that we’re not normal diversity” (INT-P48, Female, Age 36).

The exclusion of Gabooye from community development projects at the community level hinders economic participation.

“.....whenever local development projects are initiated, they seldom recruit members of the Gabooye sub-clan, even if these projects are implemented in our localities. It communicates that we are not considered contributors to the development of one’s own community” (INT-P49, Male, 39).

Gabooye majority neighborhoods suffer from severe spatial segregation, as well as a lack of basic infrastructure, sanitation, and essential services.

“.....we are driven to the outskirts of cities, where the roads are unpaved, public services are barely there. It is like being on a different planet to just a few blocks away sticking” (INT-P50, Male, 53).

Poor urban planning has intensified environmental hazards like flooding.

‘...the floodwaters come every year and every year our homes are the worst affected. There’s no drainage, no zoning for us. As if our lives are worth less’ (INT-P51, Female, 47).

With Gabooye communities having no space for children to play safely, this social exclusion begins early.

“.....our kids have no place where they can play because all public places are dangerous and every street is full of garbage and there are parks far away to play in. They grow up seeing that as their place in the world separate and unequal.” (INT-P52, Female, 39).

Businesses do not want to invest in Gabooye areas and this further sows economic deprivation.

“.....when businesses newly open in the city, they do not go to our area. This isn’t just about lack of investment, this is actively avoiding it, which kind of says how deep-seated the stigma is” (INT-P53, M, 44).

Many of the essential public services such as sanitation, electricity and security are de-prioritized, resulting in Gabooye communities being neglected.

“.....to get services such as sanitation, electricity, or help from the police, here it’s a battle. We are often told there are limited resources, but it’s plain we’re not a priority” (INT-P54, Female, 50).

Not only do these urban inequities shape the tenor of everyday life, but they also reproduce structural exclusion that prevents Gabooye areas from becoming economically vibrant and socially integrated.

Discussion

Historical Factors

Marginalization of the Gabooye community can be traced back to thousands of years of cumulative exclusion via conquest, colonialism and post-colonial political systems. Oral histories of the kingdoms of Tumaal and Yibir have never appeared in written documents; yet, oral history for Gabooye symbolically represents a counter-narrative to the dominant discourse regarding subaltern pasts. In this manner, oral history for the Gabooye functions in similar ways to oral history for many other marginalized African communities such as the San, Pygmy, Tuareg, Nubians and Berbers. Oral history is a powerful tool for self-identification and as such is a form of cultural resistance against a dominant history (Asante, 2019; Mbiti, 1990; Vansina, 1985). and allows Gabooye to define themselves while challenging the dominant historical narratives of both the Somali state and international academic circles and articulating a new narrative of belonging and dignity (Mbiti, 1990).

The Gabooye are an artisan caste located at the bottom rungs of the hierarchical structure of Somalis who traditionally organized society based on clan and caste (Cerulli, 1957; Kirk, 1904; Grottaneli, 1972). While clans were responsible for managing social hierarchy and controlling access to resources, protection and mobility, the Gabooye’s exclusion from these honor-based clans resulted in their being socially marginalized. Colonial rule exacerbated the marginality of the Gabooye. Because of its use of indirect rule, Britain relied upon the dominant clans as middlemen and further institutionalized the existing social hierarchies (Vitturini, 2020a). The colonial policies that favored pastoralist clans did not alleviate the exclusion of the Gabooye from local governance, rather they reinforced the socio-spatial marginalization of the Gabooye including confining the Gabooye physically to the periphery of cities and districts such as Daami in Hargeisa that generations of Gabooye families continue to inhabit.

On the other hand, the colonial era offered limited opportunities for the Gabooye to assert themselves politically. In the 1950s, the Gabooye organized a public meeting in Hargeisa where they elected a traditional leader and requested official recognition as a diya-paying group (Vitturini, 2017: p.50). The official recognition granted them some ability to negotiate compensation and participate in the 1959 legislative election, a unique example of “inclusion” (inclusion) within the institutional framework. Those achievements, however, were exceptions in a broader framework of exclusion (marginality). The colonial government’s tax and commercial policy, which emphasized livestock-based commerce dominated by powerful clans, undermined the artisanal economy of the Gabooye (Ekman, 2021: p.140; Vitturini,

2020b). Urbanization, which created new areas of labor for the Gabooye, did not allow for structural mobility because the work they engaged in remained precarious and stigmatized both economically and socially (Vitturini, 2020b).

This pattern of exclusion continued throughout the post-colonial era. Following the independence and unification of Somalia in 1960, the Gabooye continued to experience political marginalization due to the persistence of clan-based politics. Although the Siyad Barre regime (1969-1991) committed itself to eliminating clanism through national statehood, it was unable to abolish social hierarchies. A few Gabooye men, including Mohamed Ali Samatar, were able to obtain posts as state and military officials. However, the community as a whole remained structurally excluded (Hoehne, (2015), Ekman, 2021: p.195). The study's participants perceived these figures as symbolic rather than transformative. They compared them to "Uncle Tom" figures representing inclusion symbolically while masking structural inequalities underneath. One participant stated that "Samatar's ascension was portrayed as a calculated gesture toward symbolic inclusion more so than as a substantive achievement for the Gabooye community."

Following the civil war and fall of the Somali state in 1991, which led to the total marginalization of the Gabooye. Although they were viewed as supporting the Barre regime, their involvement in urban conflict zones also served as grounds for them to be targeted with retribution, specifically in Hargeisa. These actions contributed to their social exclusion and internal displacement during the initial stages of peace negotiations (Vitturini, 2020b: p.153; p.270). While the predominant clans established the basis for Somaliland's polity through reconciliation conferences and power-sharing agreements, the Gabooye were left out of both customary legitimacy frameworks based on lineage/clan elders/negotiated diya-paying networks. By the end of the 1990s, as a result of their prolonged marginalization, the Gabooye have been reincorporated into Somali society, yet continue to exist within subordinate roles and have minimal influence over decision making or resource distribution.

The marginalization that was created by the pre-colonial social stratification of jobs, continued with the colonial creation of laws defining social hierarchy and has been continued after colonialism through political exclusion demonstrates that Gabooye marginalization is structural rather than an accident. Although there were some attempts at marginalizing the Gabooye less during the latter stages of the colonial period and under the Barre regime, they did nothing to change the systemic manner in which they have historically been excluded. As Ekman (2021:P.256) describes, the clan-based system of democracy in Somaliland continues to reproduce historic inequality while disguising it as a legitimate custom. This system of governance also continues to create barriers that prevent marginalized groups like the Gabooye from accessing political representation, land, work and ultimately self-worth.

Sociocultural Factors

The marginalization of the Gabooye in Somaliland is not only a historical or economic issue, but also culturally symbolic. A major reason for the exclusion of the Gabooye lies in the widespread stories telling that the Gabooye are spiritually unclean people with "impure" origins that justify their exclusion. In addition to these cultural legends, within oral traditions among Somalis, there is a strong belief that the Gabooye are outside the dominant forms of "Somaliness," which is often defined as being noble, Arab-based pastoralists (Eno, 2005: p.40; Ekman, 2021: p. 168).

Kusow and Eno (2014) have shown how these kinds of exclusionary processes are a key part of developing a homogeneous identity project that 'devaluates difference while failing to celebrate diversity.' Because of the degree of such stories in daily customs of the family and community, participants told us that Gabooye children know early on that they don't belong to mainstream Somalia. These stories are passed down from generations to generations, providing young Gabooye's sense of where they fit in their world and what they hope for.

The study found that the myths about the spiritual impurities of the Gabooye are not only beliefs but operating logics that guide all aspects of every day life including where someone lives, where he or she works, who he/she can marry and where they may pray. The Gabooye are usually prevented from

participating in public events like ceremonies and other rituals simply because they are considered polluted and bring shame. Weber's concept of status group illustrates this logic: in addition to material deprivation, the cultural exclusion of the Gabooye is responsible for reproducing their marginalization and attaching shame to their identities (Ekman, 2021: p. 220-222).

The exclusion is evident especially in marriage practices. Endogamy is strictly applied against the Gabooye; powerful clans will not permit them to enter their lineages and use either fear of social contagion or spiritual impurity as excuses (Ekman, 2021: p.173). Participants stated that engagements were cancelled formally or informally when a Gabooye ancestor was discovered, public shame was experienced by many, and some participants indicated annulments occurred after legally binding agreements had been entered into. This resembles caste based systems such as India's wherein enforcers of caste cannot be violated by Dalits, families and clan members are prohibited from intermarrying and subjecting themselves to forced endogamy and ritual exclusion (Ekman, 2021: p.172; Eno, 2005: p.49). Spatial segregation further compounds this cultural exclusion. Although there are no formal regulations, a particular area of Hargeisa called Daami has been identified by the respondents as an area "out-of-bounds" for Gabooye. Invisible boundaries similar to those faced by the Osu in Nigeria and Burakumin in Japan have been created by realtors, property owners and community leaders. As we see today these stigmas continue to limit housing, market access and participation in public spaces for the Osu and Burakumin (Ekman, 2021: p.22).

These obstacles have proven to be quite resilient in the wake of Somaliland's modernization and urbanization reforms. As Vitturini (2020b) has noted, "the city has not brought an end to exclusions, but has instead organized them anew." Exclusion was dismantled when new forms of institutional inclusion, such as schools and job markets were established, however they replicated clan-based discriminatory practices. School bullying and/or neglect, along with the low quality of schooling that resulted from tracking, undermined the academic aspirations of Gabooye students (Vitturini, 2020b).

Schools have been identified as one of the earliest locations for participants' experiences of Gabooye identity. While curriculum does not explicitly include clan affiliation, peer monitoring and inaction by educators lead to student awareness of their status. Teachers often frame incidents of exclusion as "cultural realities" that validate and justify discriminatory practices. For numerous participants, the impact of this form of early educational trauma led to a loss of interest in attending school, resulting in many Gabooye students dropping out.

Similarly, there is evidence of symbolic dimensions of exclusion found within workplace interactions. In addition to vendors and service providers noting that their customers from the dominant clans would not purchase goods from the Gabooye; especially in certain types of trade such as shoe-making or hair styling. This reluctance was not related to the products themselves but to the fact that the product had come into contact with Gabooye hands. Stigma associated with specific types of labor illustrate how social purity ideologies continue to influence economic decisions.

Weber and Gramsci each theorized that cultural standards are created to support those in positions of power. Cultural standards are used as a means of creating the illusion that oppression is natural. The Gramscian approach to hegemony posits that societies with similar exclusionary views can maintain dominance through embedding the values and classification systems in common routines to create an appearance of normalcy, morality, and traditionality (Gramsci, 2020). Many of the participants reported that they have internalized these definitions and therefore felt inferior or resigned to their position. However, there were a few participants who believed that history, recognition and pride could be restored through education, media and activism.

This represents a potential cultural turning point, particularly among the young Gabooye who have access to anti-discrimination messages across the globe via diasporic networks or online media. Thus, while the research confirmed that exclusion exists in Somaliland toward Gabooye similarly to caste stigma, this phenomenon is now reinforced not merely by formal organizations but by personal relationships and culturally imagined norms. Changing this state will require more than simply a legal shift; it requires a

collective social reckoning about the myths upon which Somali identity rests and the exclusionary roles that these myths play.

Somaliland should look to India and Nigeria where lessons learned regarding successful efforts at public consciousness changing legislation provide insight into ways Somaliland may begin to address its own exclusionary culture.

Systematic Factors

The systemic exclusion of the Gabooye is perhaps most clearly articulated through institutional domains; education, employment, and participation in politics through which institutional barriers not only act as remnants of inequality but also agents of exclusion. The study highlights education deprivation as a key constraint to the upward mobility of the Gabooye. While education is universally seen as a means of social mobility, participants in the study described school as ultimately exclusionary spaces, where children face bullying, neglect, and stigmatization, sometimes even from some teachers and danger from their peers. This experience causes many Gabooye students to drop out early, where common reasons for leaving school include lack of support, low expectations, and fear of embarrassment. Those narratives resonate with findings by Ekman (2021) and Vitturini (2020b), who suggest institutional neglect of schools in Somaliland reproduces and maintains social hierarchies.

Teachers themselves are often complicit, too. Participants said educators frequently overlooked abuse directed at Gabooye students or subtly reinforced discriminatory concepts, by giving them menial roles or inquiring about their academic potential. This observation supports Weber's understanding of status based exclusion and complements research on caste based differences in education in India, with which Dalit students experience comparable interactions to institutional actors (Ekman, 2021: P.172; P.43).

The lack of remedial policies merely perpetuates the inequality. Somaliland does not provide affirmative action or other focused financial assistance to disadvantaged groups, unlike India's reservation system or Nigeria's scholarship programs for Osu students (Ekman, 2021: P.256). As a result, even academically successful students from the Gabooye community do not typically continue their studies, either on a financial basis or by having the necessary social support. On the whole, dominant clan families commonly instruct their children not to befriend their Gabooye classmates, isolating them in the classroom (Ekman, 2021: P.220).

Clan based hiring mechanisms clearly point to systemic exclusion in the employment sector. Respondents recounted job interviews that shifted abruptly in tone after they disclosed their surname, or businesses that openly declined to hire Gabooye applicants even when they matched qualifications. These practices reflect what Ekman (2021) refers to as a "clan labor market," in which access to jobs is determined by kinship ties rather than merit. This finding reflects patterns of exclusion experienced by both Osu and Burakumin spoken about previously, in the sense that they too are denied access to mainstream sectors of the labour market as a result of inherited stigma (Vitturini, 2020). Even when Gabooye members manage to get jobs, they seldom rise. Participants said a "glass ceiling" exists in which promotion and leadership roles are out of reach no matter how long someone is with the organization or how well they perform. Although the Gabooye are often symbolically represented in workplaces that profess to have an inclusion agenda, they are not empowered.

This is a manifestation of Gramscian hegemony, in which the representation of diversity is made politically acceptable even as it perpetuates structural inequities (Gramsci, 2020). For Gramscian hegemony, that can mean that symbolic incorporation inclusion in the media, token political appointments or public declarations of equality can mask real structural inequalities within a society. Antonio Gramsci made the central point that hegemony operates not just by a coercive state, but by using civil society to manufacture consent and buy in. This consent is cultivated through dominant cultural institutions education systems, religious organizations, media which infuse the 'common sense' of a population, codifying inequality as natural or inevitable. Consequently, subordinate groups might engage in institutions that perpetuate their marginalization, confusing symbolic inclusion for true change.

Marxist theories of labor reproduction also confirm this trend. These theories show how the dominant group maintains its concentration of economic power and thus control of the ideological and institutional gatekeepers. For example, schools and religious institutions are considered part of the ideological state apparatus that reproduce the current class structures by inculcating the dominant ideologies into the subordinated groups (Althusser, 1970). Also, in a similar fashion, Bourdieu & Passeron (1977) demonstrate how educational systems reproduce social hierarchies by providing legitimacy to the cultural capital of the dominant class as merit and thereby maintaining practices of exclusion. Therefore, although the Gabooye may be “included” in terms of naming or appearance, they remain outside the actual mechanisms that produce institutional power and social capital.

Entrepreneurship is also a poor sanctuary. Credit and capital access are frequently unavailable to Gabooye business owners, who repeatedly cite bank refusals and difficulties obtaining business licenses in informal enterprises. Exclusions are not caused by risk assessments, but rather by assumptions of inferior status. Financial institutions within Somali society mirror the wider clan biases that exacerbate economic marginalization of the Gabooye (Ekman 2021: p.177; Vitturini 2020b). Consequently, Somalis live in an economically closed world, wherein the ruling clans divide wealth amongst their own alliances and the remainder of society is either dependent or impoverished.

In general, the Gabooye are politically marginalized because it is by design. Somaliland’s clan-based power-sharing system does not provide any institutional means for minority groups to achieve proportional representation. Although Somaliland has a multi-party electoral system, clan is still the engine of political power. Participants indicate their failed electoral efforts and disqualifications from candidacy, tokenistic positions that have little influence. This aligns with Luling’s (2006) characterization of genealogical privilege in Somali politics. Historically, it has been argued that Somali society is largely structured around a segmented clan system where genealogy is used as an organizing principle for social organization, political allegiance and means of distributing resources (Luling, 2006).

Although they have some level of political representation in Somaliland as such as Guurti member, Member of Parliament (with the most votes regarding 2021 elections), deputy minister and civil servant, they cannot make contributions to increase Gabooye mobility. Their presence serves only to provide representation. Thus we see once again Gramscian hegemony where symbolic inclusion of various lifestyles is provided to create a very thin veneer on top of deep-seated structural inequalities (Gramsci, 2020).

Therefore, ultimately the experiences of the Gabooye illustrate that marginalization in Somaliland is neither incidental nor residual. Rather, it is structural and systemic due to the overlapping systems of exclusion based on lineages, labor and loyalty. This supports theoretically the understanding that structural inequality self-reproduces through normalized systems of classification and control as well as through systems of economic exploitation.

Conclusion

Although Gabooye speak the same language, adhere to the same religion, and have the same nationality as the majority of the Somali population, this study demonstrates that they are still systematically excluded from Somaliland’s political, economic, and social lives. Exclusion of the Gabooye cannot be solely attributed to an economic disadvantage. Instead, the historical structure of social hierarchy; based upon stigmatizing occupations, identity constructions rooted in race, and institutionally-based exclusion within educational institutions, employment sectors, and governmental systems; function to exclude them.

This study expands our knowledge base of caste by examining the ways in which symbolic shame and structural oppression collaborate to perpetuate caste-like conditions of marginalization in a formally-egalitarian society. Employing constructivist grounded theory, this study combined interview and oral history methods, along with archival materials to demonstrate that the persistent exclusion of the Gabooye is a complex multi-faceted phenomenon. Colonial and post-colonial administrations

strengthened existing hierarchical structures. Socially-cultural forms of exclusion are produced and sustained through mythologies regarding impurities, geographical separation, and restrictions on marriage. Schools, employers, and governmental agencies continue to produce and support these discriminatory attitudes. Although there were periods during which political inclusion allowed for temporary alterations in perception regarding the Gabooye (such as when they were included as citizens during the Siyad Barre regime), the underlying framework of marginalization was never dismantled.

This research extends sociological theory by applying Weberian status group theory, caste analysis, and Gramscian theories of hegemony to the Somali context. Additionally, this study builds on and localizes Kusow and Eno's (2014) critique of Somali identity formation – which excludes groups such as the Gabooye through a racialized and genealogical logic. Through its use of empirically-derived data from Hargeisa, this study enhances the global knowledge base of caste-like exclusion in non-Hindu, Muslim-majority countries and provides a case study of Somalia for broader debates surrounding ethnicity, stratification and recognition.

Additionally, the findings of this study suggest urgent policy implications. True inclusion will not result solely from economic programs. It requires: 1) the destruction of inherited cultural myths; 2) the creation of affirmative action opportunities in both education and employment; 3) the formal acknowledgment of Gabooye voices in political processes. Educational policy initiatives focused specifically on addressing stigma; anti-discrimination laws; and inclusive media narratives represent potential first steps. Civil society organizations and government bodies must develop strategies to reduce stigma through narrative development, representation and legislative reform.

This study presents a detailed and grounded example of urban exclusion in Hargeisa. However, it opens doors for additional investigation. For instance: future research may focus on the experience of rural or village Gabooye communities; examine gendered aspects of stigma; and investigate how inter-generational trauma evolves and develops over time. Comparative studies among various regions in Somalia or between similar groups of marginalized people in Africa or Asia can potentially improve theoretical constructs. A longitudinal research methodology can provide insight into how community responses shift due to factors including globalization, urbanization and diasporic connection.

Ultimately, achieving equality for the Gabooye will involve more than simply creating laws or providing economic assistance. Equality for the Gabooye will depend upon fundamentally changing how belonging, honor, and history are understood in Somali society. As long as Somali society continues to define these concepts in the same way, systemic exclusion will find new forms, while retaining their traditional characteristics.

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